

6G Function Modularity: Benefits, Challenges, and Options

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Abstract—*Network Modularization, i.e., the refactoring of the functionalities of 5G Network Functions (NFs), will be an important tool to meet future requirements in the 6G System (6GS). In particular, via network modularization, it is possible to streamline the NF compositions and the inter-NF interactions. However, to achieve the highest possible efficiency without loss on inter-operability, we need a clear understanding of the different Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and modularization techniques which are required to achieve the necessary end-to-end performance. In this work, we investigate the KPIs, the modularization methods prioritized by the research community, and the industrial implications thereof. We also outline the orchestration requirements for the successful integration of modules to 6GS and the one possible integration of quantum technology to solve the synchronization challenge.*

Index Terms—6G, SBA, network virtualization, network modularization, flexibility, efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

6G needs to be able to support a wide range of use cases with stringent requirements in addition to all the services supported by 5G within an economically viable business model. Moreover, the rate at which society transitions, moving away from fossil fuels, has exacerbated clean energy consumption, thus leading to an increased demand for a more energy-efficient and flexible network architecture. Flexibility and efficiency have also been the central building blocks in 5G networks. The Service Based Architecture (SBA) allows network operators to cluster 5G Core (5GC) functionalities into specific NFs, i.e., standardized and implemented separately. The NFs can be flexibly deployed in different locations and can be scaled more dynamically according to local needs. However, when introducing NFs, some potential performance hurdles need to be overcome. For example, inter-NF dependencies of the Fifth Generation (5G) architecture might cause increased signaling and data exchange. Moreover, in some deployments, the time to complete specific 5GC procedures is higher than their 4G counterparts, as shown in [1].

To enable flexibility without increasing complexity, a 6GS needs an easily deployable architecture of modules that can scale and change based on current needs [2]. 6G needs to build upon efficiency gains of the previous generation, preserving the already optimized aspects before streamlining NFs and procedures where needed. Moreover, the new 6G architecture

needs to provide higher flexibility, avoiding the need for dedicated implementation and deployment scenarios. Through an End-to-End (E2E) reevaluation of 5G System (5GS), it is possible to outline how the new architecture needs to evolve to be more flexible and scalable, reduce overhead, and be more efficient [3]. One aspect is that the NFs should be designed in a self-contained structure with as little dependency as possible on other 6G NFs. The decreased inter-NF dependency would lead to fewer interfaces and processing points, which improves the efficiency of the procedures and signalling. Also, this approach provides a smoother introduction of new functions and services in the future.

Network modularisation targets to decompose the 6GS into orthogonal building blocks (i.e., NFs, services, and interfaces) with the right level of granularity. The modular design of the network functions bring an opportunity to place the NFs or functionalities that are dependent on each other in the same module. By eliminating the inter-function dependencies and maximizing the relevance of the NF functionalities within a module, modular design can optimize signaling and latency. The use of virtualization allows for the optimal placement of NFs, their migration, or cloning. The modularisation of the NFs needs to be performed with an E2E vision in mind, considering not only the network function granularity but also the necessary interfaces and deployment options to incorporate existing and new technologies such as Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN), network programmability, and Everything-as-a-Service (XaaS), etc. Moreover, the security implications of network modularisation need to be also considered, including but not limited to the management of trust among different entities, i.e., network modules, layers, or slices [3]. To further enhance the efficiency, it is also possible to integrate Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) into the network modules, supporting the adaptation into NFs deployment.

In this paper, we discuss network modularisation for the 6G era, focusing on the optimized network function decomposition and the streamlined network function interfaces and interactions. Our contributions to this paper can be listed as follows:

- We define KPIs that need to be considered in the 6G modularisation;
- We present several modularisation concepts and granularity options with a con/pro analysis;

This paper is reflective of Hexa-X-II's view on the subject and does not necessarily represent the individual view form any associated companies.

- We further investigate the E2E implications of the modular 6GC.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the relevant works on 5G SBA design and the attempts to provide a modular 6GC. We also outline a few use cases that can utilize the modular design. Different approaches to 6G modularity are detailed in Section III, underlining the different decomposition strategies. Section III-D analyzes the E2E implications of a modular architecture. Finally, Section IV summarizes the benefits and implications of a modular 6GS, and Section V concludes the paper.

II. BACKGROUND

The efforts to create a modular and efficient network topology started from earlier generations. The 4G network has introduced the Control and User Planes Separation paradigm (CUPS), which lies in separating NFs responsible for signaling (CP) and handling user data streams (UP). The CP entities typically handle different transactions implementing different CP services like Mobility Management (MM), Resource Management (RM), etc. The proposed separation has enabled the independent placement of CP and UP NFs. The placement and the number of the NF instances depend on network topology and are driven by required network performance optimization. Typically, requested optimization tries to minimize network reaction time and the overall traffic volume. However, the low granularity of CP NFs causes low flexibility.

To overcome the limitation of the flexibility of 4G, the 5G core is built upon the SBA, where the CP NFs have a high degree of functional decomposition. In this architecture, NFs (e.g., AMF, UPF, etc.) interact with each other to execute 5G procedures, e.g., UE registration or handover [2]. An important feature of 5GC is the ability to add new CP NFs, using request/response and subscribe/notify mechanisms, that can interact with other NFs to create more advanced CP services. 5GC CP NFs can be implemented in the cloud which gives several benefits. Firstly, the scaling mechanism of the cloud can allocate resources to a virtualized NF if needed. Second, virtualized NFs can be migrated or cloned during network runtime. An important performance implication of SBA in 5GC is the delay in transferring and processing CP messages. The transfer delay in virtualized networks comprises a component related to the physical distance between NFs, a delay related to a message bus, and a delay related to virtualization (typically not negligible). The processing delay on the other hand can be nicely controlled by allocating resources to a NF using scaling. The use of customized techniques can optimize the virtualization-related delay as well, selection of the inter-NF message passing mechanism can optimize this type of delay in 5G has been noticed to be a bottleneck.

However, in SBA, the high inter-NF dependency and interactions (i.e., via http/2) might cause low signaling performance and significant message transfer latency. In addition to that, the future network is predicted to have an increased infrastructure complexity due to the need to integrate the near-edge and the far-edge with the Cloud Continuum [6]. The 5G CN

setup is purely based on the SBI procedures and does not introduce any additional specific signaling between any NFs. However, the Nx interfaces (N1, N2, N3 etc) still use point-to-point signaling between two NFs, with specific standardized signaling. As an example, the RAN-CN communication is via the N2 interface and always through the AMF (regardless of the NF in CN being the “final destination”). Any CN NF accessing RAN needs to go via the AMF. Procedures supported over N2 are PDU Session Management, UE Context Management, UE MM, Paging, Transport of NAS Messages, NG Interface Management, etc.

A modular 6G architecture needs to consider all these challenges of the previous generations. The modularization study starts with determining the optimal granularity level of a module and to evaluate the feasibility of module granularity for a use case, [1] proposes three evaluation metrics, i.e., E2E packet processing latency, control plane latency, and throughput. Extending these evaluation metrics, [8] presents a module design method, i.e., built upon the relevance of different micro-services. More specifically, they propose that the micro-services with higher relevancy with each other should be placed within the same module while the services that are not dependent on each other can be placed in different modules. On the other hand, [8] does not provide how to formulate the inter-service relevance or dependency, which is the key requirement.

III. MODULAR 6G NETWORKS

To be able to improve flexibility, decrease overhead, and increase scalability and efficiency of 6G networks, there is a need to analyze the different NFs within the 5G core architecture and understand the dependencies between these functions, how they interact with each other to deliver E2E services, and how the architecture needs to be evolved for the next generation. One aspect of 6G NFs should be that they are designed to be as self-contained as possible and with minimum dependency on each other. By reducing dependencies, there

Fig. 1: Decomposition of 5G NFs with changing granularity and methods

TABLE I: Advantages and drawbacks of fine-grained modularisation

Advantages	Disadvantages
Scalability management: efficient and targeted scale-up and scale-down of the resources assigned to the fine-grained modules.	Performance: the latency increases when traversing more modules to complete the NF execution.
Maintenance: easier to identify, isolate, and replace faulty fine-grained modules.	Interfaces definition: interfaces between modules should be defined for cross-vendor deployments.
Development: faster when developing different independent modules in parallel, and flexible when selecting programming languages and processing platforms.	Management: Managing a bigger number of modules and their interactions increases the management overhead.
Deployment: flexible in placing modules in distributed deployments.	Signaling: more signaling and data exchange is needed between fine-grained modules.
Reusability: Efficient when reusing fine-grained modules in different implementations.	Context data management: more memory transactions are needed by the modules to read and store stateful data.

will be fewer interfaces and processing points and, thus, the possibility to improve the procedures and signaling. Also, this approach provides a smoother introduction of new functions and services in the future. The analysis should also focus on recognizing real-time KPIs to develop mechanisms that are able to dynamically adapt NFs to changing network conditions (i.e., changing traffic patterns, user demands, and network state) [8]. As the definition of relevance depends on the use case, there are multiple granularity and decomposition options, cf. Fig.1. Modular design can also be used to optimize the functional composition to meet specific KPI targets. However, the functionality of an NF should not be removed from the module design only to reduce complexity [7]. This section details the trade-offs and dependencies between various NFs to optimize their composition for improved KPIs.

A. KPIs towards modular 6GC

The evaluation of architecture and procedures is quite challenging, as a multitude of design criteria must be considered that affect the KPIs, including but not limited to

- the affinity constraints, e.g. the nodes are meant to be placed in different physical locations;
- latency limitations, which concern how a procedure is constructed based on the current architecture;
- reliability requirements, that manifest themselves in affinity and anti-affinity rules, persistent memory, etc;
- new technologies, e.g. cloud, virtualization, IP protocols, and quantum technologies;
- unique requirements posed by the use cases such as Joint Communication and Sensing;
- signaling traffic volume;
- self-sufficiency, i.e., indicates how many times a certain function depends on another function to complete a task;
- backward compatibility;
- the number of failure points that indicates how many times a functional entity requires a re-start of a procedure resulting from a failure to send/receive a message;
- service (including CP/Management Plane services) reaction time (delay) and other factors understood as service KPIs;
- Service-CP/CP/MP overhead (control/management traffic volume minimization);
- easiness of functions migration and cloning without disturbing other services;

- separation of concerns;
- ability to provide highly reliable solutions (fast delegation of functions to other NFs in case of failures, etc.).

However, most of these aspects cannot be evaluated analytically. For the optimum module compositions, several procedures should be evaluated, for different architectural options. The different deployments can, e.g., be how the NFs are defined, distributed RAN and CN, and centralized solutions.

B. Modularisation granularity

The granularity of the NF modules is a critical aspect of deciding on a modular 6GS. Specifically, it is important to decide on the number of modules and sub-modules and the logic to incorporate into each module and sub-module. To properly select the right granularity level, it is necessary to understand the implications (advantages and drawbacks) of those selections. The advantages and drawbacks of fine-granularity modules are presented in Table I. In general, the increase in the module granularity would lead to a higher degree of flexibility in terms of scalability management, maintenance, development, and deployment. However, this enhanced flexibility comes at the cost of decreased performance (i.e., longer latency), increased signaling overhead, and higher complexity in terms of interface definition, module management, and context data management. Figure 2 depicts the trade-off between performance and flexibility based on the degree of modularisation granularity.

C. Modularisation strategies

In addition to the modular granularity, the decomposition strategy becomes critical for an efficient 6GS.

1) *Procedure-based decomposition*: Following the approach proposed in [5], core NFs can be redesigned such that each NF includes the logic for executing a complete procedure such as PDU session establishment, UE registration, UE deregistration, etc. This results in a new functional architecture of the core network compared to the current architecture, which distributes the logic required to execute a complete procedure among different NFs. For example, one procedure-based NF would be the “UE Registration NF” which is composed of the processing logic required to execute the UE registration procedure, which is distributed according to the 5G specifications over the following 5G NFs: AMF, AUSF, PCF, NRF, UDM, and UDR.

Fig. 2: Impact of modularization granularity on performance and flexibility.

Such a design provides better performance in terms of the reduced volume of signaling between NFs, shorter time needed to complete the execution of a functional procedure, and easier management of the UE context and NFs state. On the other hand, such a design limits the flexibility in developing, deploying, and managing the more coarse granular NFs as discussed in Section III-A.

2) *Service KPI-driven decomposition*: The 6G CP NFs are expected to be virtualised (cloud-native), which, by advance in the case of the Cloud Continuum (CC), allows flexible orchestration and placement that can possibly break the current split of a system into different orchestration domains.

The decomposition of CP into services provides the opportunity for a service-centric approach, in contrast to the function-centric approach used in previous generations of mobile networks. In this approach, it is assumed that a certain service of CP is using several service-specific NFs (NF chain). The distinction between this approach and the procedure-based decomposition approach explained previously is that the creation of the services is done dynamically to adapt to KPI requirements. It allows for runtime optimization of KPIs of a predefined CP service using the following mechanisms:

- **Dynamic migration of NFs** using reactive or proactive approach (data-driven, for example, following users' mobility). In this approach, a new placement of NF reduces reaction time and service traffic volume;
- **Cloning of NFs**. The service chain analysis may lead to identifying NF clusters with intensive signaling. In the original configuration, the identified clusters are handled centrally. On the contrary, after creating clones of some functions, more operations can be handled locally. Such local handling contributes to quick reaction time and traffic volume reduction; however, the exchange of information between cloned NFs has to be taken into account;
- **On-the-fly compiling of 'macro NFs' out of highly granular NFs** Minimizing the delay and traffic in inter-NF interactions of NFs that are placed in the same DC. However such delay is significant even in a single DC,

Fig. 3: Example of optimization options of a Control Plane Service consisting of four NFs deployed in three data centres: a) Initial placement of NFs; b) NF1 migration; c) NF1 cloning; d) Creating of macro-NF by compiling together NF3 and NF4.

and the SBA communication can also add non-negligible delay. However, creating such a macro function takes time, and the possibility of decomposing it back into highly granular NFs can be allowed. The operation allows for creating a service composed of NFs with different granularity.

To implement the service decomposition approach, a dedicated function that continuously evaluates the deployed service KPIs (e.g. reaction time, traffic volume) has to be added. The above-mentioned operations have to be driven by a dedicated service orchestrator that, on the basis of the analysis of the service and its properties, takes decisions on NF migration, NF cloning, or NF-macro creation. As the optimized services have to interact with each other, the placement of a function that acts as an inter-service gateway needs to be developed. During the service lifetime, the dynamicity of NF placement changes based on the operator policy but each configuration is costly and the cost should be evaluated for each service reconfiguration.

D. Streamlined interactions and management

In addition to the decomposition strategy, streamlining NF interfaces and communications by optimizing and simplifying the inter-module interactions is critical for an efficient and flexible network. The inter-module signaling as well as the increased orchestration decision volume, bring the need for further optimization of network modules based on deployment decisions and the implementation of SBI for state synchronization [1]. In order to increase the efficiency, the existing interfaces/procedures must be enhanced where needed, and the redundant or absolute interactions must be removed [9]. The different network modularization granularities and the need to

deploy the modules throughout the extended Cloud Continuum landscape (spanning from centralized cloud, through Near, Far, and on-premise edge cloud) will introduce a high level of complexity in the E2E network management that the 6G Orchestration and Management layer need to address. As a matter of fact, managing such challenging scenarios will require the orchestrators to evolve from scripts or complex workflow to an “intent-based” form of orchestration where the service requirement is expressed as high-level intentions rather than specific tasks. Moreover, the 6G Orchestration system should be able to function in a completely autonomous manner, ideally without human interaction. The recent developments in machine learning and AI techniques represent the key enablers to such autonomous operations. In regards to this matter, the orchestration system should avoid static workflows but it should be based on simple basic actions that the AI system is able to compose in order to fulfill the intent-based service requirements.

The orchestration in the 6G network may benefit for the recent advances in quantum technologies to enhance modular streamlined interactions while maintaining precision in inter-module signaling. Quantum synchronization plays a key role in facilitating the distribution of entanglement across different network modules, thereby promoting the distributed nature of the network [10]. However, implementing quantum synchronization in a modular network requires careful consideration of the quantum technologies involved, the synchronization objectives, and the complexities inherent in it. By exploring hybrid approaches that integrate classical synchronization methods alongside quantum synchronization, a more adaptable solution can be achieved to effectively address KPIs such as latency and resilience. Nevertheless, the management of a hybrid classical-quantum network requires the definition of interfaces for 6G network modules to accommodate both classical and quantum communication resources. As a result, maintaining a clear separation between the data and control planes becomes essential for effective orchestration.

IV. KEY TAKEAWAYS

Increasing the modularity of the NFs and streamlining the inter-module interactions have the potential to maximize the flexibility and efficiency of future networks. However, in addition to the envisioned KPI improvements, a modular 6GS would bring various challenges and implications. Table II presents a summary of network modularization’s envisioned KPI improvements, requirements, and needed compute resources.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we focus on the network modularization concept and its applicability in 6G networks. Based upon the principle of increasing the relevance of the functionalities inside the same module and minimizing the inter-module dependencies, we first present the KPIs and KVIs that need to be considered in the modularization. We also analyzed the advantages and disadvantages of fine-grained modularization.

TABLE II: Benefits and implications of modularization in 6G

Envisioned KPI improvement	Low latency & procedure completion time, decreased CP signaling, same front-haul user-plane traffic, reduced complexity, direct signaling, efficiency (i.e., fewer interfaces, etc.), network scalability, flexibility (i.e., both deployment and execution), reliability
Requirements	Management functions between RAN and CN, changing the core NF design and implementation. Interfaces might be needed for inter-node network-level coordination. Redesign of the architecture considering new approaches
Standard relations	23.501, 23.502, 38.413, RAN modules defined in 38.401. O-RAN considers an open-interfaced disaggregated RAN, 3GPP
Computing resources	All the solutions are mostly software-based

Based on the KPIs and the trade-offs, we present two modularization strategies. Finally, we outline the need for streamlined NFs, their interactions, and E2E management.

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